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Color engineering of fluorescent material and detection

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Abstract

Every color is not fluorescent, but every fluorescent has color property. Every fluorescent material should glow, but every color has no glowing property. Fluorescent has brightness property. But every bright color/material is not fluorescent. The key contradiction to color scientist relies between/among reflection, refractive materials, and fluorescent materials. Fluorescent material glows in night vision rather than the property of general reflection, refractive materials, and bright materials. Fluorescent dyes can be said as night glowing dyes. Scientist and research confuse the technology of fluorescent behind the reflective materials. There is lack of clarity between fluorescent and reflective materials Therefore, an approach on color engineering of fluorescent material has been remarked by the phenomena of energy, glow, reflection, and performance color.

Keywords

Fluorescent material, color performance, energy, technical textiles

1. Introduction

Fluorescent is an optical brightener or color brightener which glows at night vision. All optical brightener are not fluorescent. So, the fluorescent can also be termed as glowing color. Scientist

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are also using the term fluorescent as brightener. In color science and technology, fluorescent is also termed as photoluminance, phosphorescence, chemiluminescence, and night glowing chromatic performance. Fluorescent has versatile technical applications, such as: fashionable dress, dancing dress, night dress, baby dress, dog dress, protection dress, traffic police dress, traffic signal, defence detection, signboard, room decoration, car decoration, and multidimensional branches in performance engineering.

Fluorescent material shows brighter due to ultraviolet radiation at day light (Mohamed Hamdaoui, 2015). Phenol ester and 9,10-diphenylanthracene (Kuniaki Okamoto) have chemiluminescence property.

2. Mechanism of fluorescent

The Franck–Condon principle states the intensities of vibronic transitions and emission of a photon (Mulliken, 1971). In fluorescence, the mechanism continues a vibrational stage from the molecules exciting stage ($E = E_0, E_1, E_2, E_3$) to relaxation stage ($E = E_3, E_2, E_1, E_0$). This is the reason of chromatic glow inside the material in the ultraviolet (UV) spectrum. The relaxation stage signifies the continuous glow of the fluorescent material. All reflective materials have no relaxation stage ($E = E_3, E_2, E_1, E_0$). So, all refractive materials ($E = E_0, E_1, E_2, E_3$) are not fluorescent material. There is limitation in general spectrometric analysis or color spectrometric analysis of a fluorescent material. The exciting stage ($E = E_0, E_1, E_2, E_3$) of fluorescent material can be shown by graphical spectra. But the relaxation stage ($E = E_3, E_2, E_1, E_0$) of fluorescent material can not be captured/displayed by the graphical spectra of the spectrometric analysis. So, UV lighting, pictorial process, and fluorescent spectrophotometer are necessary to show the glow of the fluorescent material. Fluorescent material controls the reflection to show the glow, equation 1 and 2. But the reflective material can not control the reflection, equation 3. Relaxation phenomena is absent in the reflective material. Instead of relaxation phenomena, reflective material scatters in multidimensional direction in terms of material shape or angular property or brightness property.

For example,

Energy of fluorescent material in exciting phenomena,

$$E = E_0, E_1, E_2, E_3, \dots, E_n \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 1}$$

Energy of fluorescent material in relaxation phenomena,

$$E = E_n, E_3, E_2, E_1, E_0 \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 2}$$

Energy of refractive material,

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$$E = E_0, E_1, E_2, E_3, \dots, E_n \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 3}$$

3. Fluorescent versus reflection

Chemically; aluminium, sand, polyester, polyamide 6 6 and 1,4-phenylene-diamine (para-phenylenediamine) have no distinct property of fluorescent. These materials have physical property of brightness due to smooth surface of structural property. Synthetic fibres, such as: Kevlar, polyester, and Polyamide 6, 6 have brightness property due to polymeric structure of crystallinity, round and fine shape. Fluorescent has a special phenomenon and established meaning in textile coloration which glow like candle in night vision. Actually, fluorescent is not a synonym of reflection or brightness. Every color has reflective property. Every color is brighter from 400 nm to 700 nm. So, the color is visible from 400 nm to 700 nm. But every color is not fluorescent. Fluorescent dyes or pigment can make the material fluorescent. Fluorescent glows in UV spectrums. Fluorescent brights in visible spectrums. In general, aluminium, sand, polyamide 6 6 and Kevlar are not fluorescent material. Reactive dyed yellow fabric is not fluorescent fabric, but fluorescent dyed yellow fabric is fluorescent fabric. Synthetic fabric may have different color in terms of pigment or dyes application. The fluorescent dyed fabric will be brighter in night vision. It is necessary to compare non-colored raw Kevlar fibre, colored Kevlar fibre, and fluorescent dyed Kevlar fibre or polyamide 6, 6 fibre for performance coloring applications and defence detection.

4. Conclusion

In spectroscopic language, the color physics can be defined as absorption, reflection, transmission, brightness, and fluorescent. The five terms of optical geometry have different spectroscopic response to the optical sensor or chromatic sensor or photoluminescent in UV, visible, and infrared spectrums.

5. Author contribution and authorship status

The author is self-declaring the authorship status in terms of conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, experimentation, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

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References

- Anwar Hossain, A. K. S., A. Bagchi, Kashmita Bhattacharya. (2016). Simultaneous Dyeing and Fragrance Finishing of Cotton Fabric. *Journal of Materials Sciences and Applications, American Association for Science and Technology (AASCIT), USA*, 2(4), 25-34.
<https://documents.pub/document/simultaneous-dyeing-and-fragrance-finishing-of-cotton-simultaneous-dyeing-and.html?page=1>
- Hossain, A. (2020). A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), *Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments* (pp. 151-170). IntechOpen.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360>
- Hossain, A. (2021a). Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 10(117), 1-11, Article 1011721-01.
<http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487>
- Hossain, A. (2021b). Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV-Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background. *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, 1-12.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074>
- Hossain, A. (2023). *Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.*

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>

- Hossain, A., Islam, A. S., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Pollution Free Dyeing on Cotton Fabric Extracted from *Swietenia macrophylla* and *Musa Acuminata* as Unpolluted Dyes and Citrus. Limon (L.) as Unpolluted Mordanting Agent. *Trends in Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 3(2), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.03.000558>
- Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. (2019). Effect of Variation in Different Mechanical Setting of Draft Change Pinion in Trutzschler Carding, Machine for Cotton and Polyester Carded Slivers. *Current Trends in Fashion Technology & Textile Engineering*, 4(4).
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Effect-of-Variation-in-Different-Mechanical-Setting-Hossain/9402f52697c08f2b6104abb07e1f4f414aa3f332>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.19080/CTFTTE.2019.04.555650>
- Hossain, A., & Samanta, A. K. (2018). Cost Minimization in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments. *Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online)*, USA.
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cost-Minimisation-in-Sample-Development-and-Process-Hossain-Samanta/ee6de04748b507cdec19cb7af66cfde0870a5b0d>;
<https://doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.04.000590>
- Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., Bhaumik, N. S., Vankar, P. S., & Shukla, D. (2018). Organic Colouration and Antimicrobial Finishing of Organic Cotton Fabric by Exploiting Distillated Organic Extraction of *Organic Tectona grandis* and *Azardirachta indica* with Organic Mordanting Compare to Conventional Inorganic Mordants. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 2018(1), 1-12.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21790.51524>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245102>
- Hossain, A., Samanta, A. K., NS, B., PS, V., & Shukla. (2018). Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker. *Journal of Textile Science & Engineering*, 8(5), 1-5. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Non-toxic-Coloration-of-Cotton-Fabric-using-and-Hossain-Samanta/76a9a8128bc038db760f2b93328e4eefeb2ae4d1>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2165-8064.1000374>
- Hossain, A., Sun, D., & Samanta, A. (2019). Modern Technology versus Rapid Economical Growth in Smart Textiles Incorporated with Encapsulated Phase Change Materials Containing Latent Heat for Special Workers and Extreme Weather Conditions. *JResLit Journal of Science and Technology*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15079.62880>;
https://pure.hw.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/92968499/Modern_Technology_versus_Rapid_Economical_Growth...pdf; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245107>
- Hossain, M. A. (17 May 2023). *Anowar's Handbook on Application of Computer in Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,

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Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23199.53923>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8237842>

Hossain, M. A. (2009). *Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology, ISBN-978-984-35-2885-8, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh* (Vol. 1-4). Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844857>

Hossain, M. A. (2010a). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials II*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29667.94247>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241586>

Hossain, M. A. (2010b). *Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer, ISBN-978-984-35-2883-4, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh*. Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844933>

Hossain, M. A. (2010c). *Principle of garments production, ISBN-978-984-35-2884-1, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh*. Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844918>

Hossain, M. A. (2015a, 26th April, 2015). *Integrated dyeing and cosmetic finishing on cotton fabric* 6th all India Inter Engineering college academic meet-2015 and Science & Technology exhibition for a sustainable society, Organised by Forum of Scientist, Engineers & Technologists (FOSET), 15N, Nelli Sengupta Sarani (Lindsay Street), Kolkata-7000087, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29340.26244>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13304637>

Hossain, M. A. (2015b). *Power Point Presentation on Combined dyeing and cosmetic finishing of woven cotton fabric for garments* (Department of Jute and Fibre technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, India, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28804.50568>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311367>

Hossain, M. A. (2015c). *Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments* [Textile Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-70019, West Bengal, India.]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15918.48965>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854437>

Hossain, M. A. (2018). *Power Point Presentation on Applications and Engineering of Geotextiles* (Department of Textile Engineering, City university, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh (engr.anowar@yahoo.com), Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17899.31521>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311345>

Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Optical engineering of fluorescent material and detection; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au

- Hossain, M. A. (2019a). Cyclodextrin for Aroma Finishing on Textile Substrate-A Review Article. *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 8(89). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11724.18561>; <http://www.ijsei.com/archive-88919.htm>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242756>
- Hossain, M. A. (2019b). Uster analysis of cotton/polyester blended spun yarns with different counts. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2019c). Uster Imperfections of 35% Cotton and 65% Polyester Blended Yarn for 40Ne, 50Ne and 60Ne Ring Spun Yarn. *South Asian Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(2). <https://www.sciencegate.app/document/10.36346/sarjet.2019.v01i02.002>; https://sarpublishation.com/media/articles/SARJET_12_43-49_c.pdf
- Hossain, M. A. (2019d). Zero Toxic Approach of Cotton Fabric Coloration with Botanical Waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as Natural Dyes and Citrus Lemon (Lemon Leaves) as Natural Mordanting Agent. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18112.75524>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850320>
- Hossain, M. A. (2020). My first presentation at PhD School for selection of PhD research proposal on camouflage textiles in 2020. Academic conference at PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Australia, Vic-3056, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7918250>, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33383.11680>.
- Hossain, M. A. (2021a). Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. *American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology*, 9(1), 31-47. <http://pubs.sciepub.com/materials/9/1/3/>
- Hossain, M. A. (2021b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination* (Presented in academic conference, First milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University, 12 February 2021, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844692>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28897.48488>
- Hossain, M. A. (2021c). Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), *Colorimetry* (pp. 1-22). IntechOpen. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.101537>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022a). Camouflage Assessment Of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV-Vis-IR Background Illumination. *Defence Science Journal*, 72(3), 359-370. <https://publications.drdo.gov.in/ojs/index.php/dsj/article/view/17731/7785>
- Hossain, M. A. (2022b). *Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration and Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Background* (Presented in humanities and

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social context conference, second milestone of PhD candidature, RMIT University; 15 February 2022, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844729>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32252.92803>

Hossain, M. A. (2022c). Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2022). Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. *Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology*, 1-16.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *50% income support and 100% life-safety compensation were requested and proposed to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29528.47360>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159331>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Academic Certificates, academic achievements and citizen identity of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anwar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33349.83689>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286740>

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). Advancement in UV-Visible-IR Camouflage Textiles and Camouflage Physics. *Scholarly Community Encyclopedia*. <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49095>

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29805.15844>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7944616>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>

Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223162>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Anowar's Handbook International Trade and Marketing Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,

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- Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25788.21120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023h). *Anowar's Handbook of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13624.72966>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240342>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023i). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12923.49448>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238071>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023j). *Anowar's Handbook on Chemistry (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15879.16801>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238806>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19654.04160>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023l). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35625.16486>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8232618>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023m). *Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-4)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16822.88641>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8239492>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023n). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Mechanical Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25368.78089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240371>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023o). *Anowar's Handbook on Elements of Theory of Machine and Machine Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University,

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28724.22405>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240388>

Hossain, M. A. (2023p). *Anowar's Handbook on Environment and Safety Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36273.97126>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240507>

Hossain, M. A. (2023q). *Anowar's Handbook on Fabric Structure and Design*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30821.37606>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240534>

Hossain, M. A. (2023r). *Anowar's Handbook on Garments Manufacturing Technology*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27465.93280>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240547>

Hossain, M. A. (2023s). *Anowar's Handbook on Industrial Economics*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34176.81925>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240589>

Hossain, M. A. (2023t). *Anowar's Handbook on Machine Technology & Maintenance of Wet Processing Machineries*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22432.76802>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240660>

Hossain, M. A. (2023u). *Anowar's Handbook on Materials Engineering and Practices*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14883.02082>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240703>

Hossain, M. A. (2023v). *Anowar's Handbook on Microprocessor, Robotics and Control Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26627.07204>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240796>

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- Hossain, M. A. (2023w). *Anowar's Handbook on Statistics for Engineer*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17714.17602>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240984>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023x). *Anowar's Handbook on Technical Textiles*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19391.89763>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241043>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023y). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Physics (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17294.74561>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241105>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023z). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Project Management*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35461.32480>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245088>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aa). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials I*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22537.62568>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241631>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ab). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing & Quality Control (Part-3)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23166.77121>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241394>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ac). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-1)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14778.16327>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241291>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ad). *Anowar's Handbook on Textile Testing and Quality Control (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34071.96169>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8241183>

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 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
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www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain, M. A. (2023ae). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-01)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19896.52484>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8233503>

Hossain, M. A. (2023af). *Anowar's Handbook on Yarn Manufacturing Technology (Part-2)*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29857.99683>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8233914>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ag). *Application for promotion as Professor (Textile Engineering) and/or right adjustment of my designation under consideration of my Curriculum Vitae (CV), publications and teaching experiences under the promotion act of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh; supported by the act of University Grants Commission of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35245.05606>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286913>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ah). *Camouflage textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for multidimensional combat backgrounds* (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Accepted on 28 March 2023; Valencia, Spain, Issue. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22550.73282>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844652>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ai). *Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Visible-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (Global Summit on Chemical Engineering and Catalysis (ISTRCEC 2023), accepted on 20 March 2023; Rome, Italy, Issue. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847802>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23969.17766>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aj). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, Second milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898707>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ak). *Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination, PhD student: 3820066, First milestone thesis for the degree of doctor of philosophy* [Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15701.50403>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898541>

- Hossain, M. A. (2023al). Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. *Advance Research in Textile Engineering*, Austin Publishing Group.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36504.98560>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297554>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023am). *Compliance, cost minimization & production support for textile industry*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11452.21127>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278881>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023an). *Conference Presentation on "Camouflage Engineering and Camouflage Textiles for Defence Technology"; 2023 Philippine Textile Congress, Future Thinking for Philippine Textiles, Philippine Textile Research Institute (PTRI), Department of Science and Technology-Central Office (DOST-CO), General Santos Avenue Bicutan, Taguig City, Metro Manila, 1631, Philippine; Speaker during the Textile for Human Security and Defense Session (Session 8) of the Congress on 20 November 2023; Accepted.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.22407>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117340>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ao). Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV-Visible-IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. *Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square* 1-18.
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ap). "Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023aq). *Decision of RMIT University against Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye did a conspiracy to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced hidden conspiracy of life threatening and notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and delegate, RMIT University*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33536.61441>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317924>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ar). *Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747451>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023as). *First Action and Support Plan at PhD School during COVID-19 in 2020, Supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26567.68006>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7923009>

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Hossain, M. A. (2023at). *Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind*. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

Hossain, M. A. (2023au). *Letter of study leave extension for PhD research works from 1st November 2023 to 31 October 2025, designated for Md. Anowar Hossain, lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, Dhaka, Bangladesh*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15384.16648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13862986>

Hossain, M. A. (2023av). *Md. Anowar Hossain, Anowar's Handbook on Polymer Science & Engineering*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31974.80969>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8240852>

Hossain, M. A. (2023aw). Md. Anowar Hossain, Video presentation of Anowar Hossain's PhD invention in PhD School, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. In. School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21104.43524>.

Hossain, M. A. (2023ax). *My declaration, acknowledgement and dedication to achieve PhD degree (Fashion & Textiles) on "camouflage textiles with technical coloration and incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds"* [Textile Engineering, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2021]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18532.65925>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898850>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ay). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my family/relative peoples for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-3)* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19378.38089>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970344>

Hossain, M. A. (2023az). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my maternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-1)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.13603/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970310>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ba). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my paternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-2)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29896.90887>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970241>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bb). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bc). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bd). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>

Hossain, M. A. (2023be). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bf). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bg). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bh). Neuro-Camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *Journal of Applied Material Science & Engineering Research*, 7(1), 67-71.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13401.90729>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bi). Neuro-camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking.

PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2710224/v1>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bj). *Non-paid salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University submitted for approval of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27962.16328>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10132457>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bk). *An optical platform of material engineering for design of camouflage product against multidimensional combat backgrounds from 400 nm to 2500 nm (Scholars World Congress on Material Science and Nanotechnology” (MatScience 2023), Accepted on 18 April 2023, Issue.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844597>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28176.28165>

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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain, M. A. (2023bl). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bm). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bn). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles against advanced surveillance of defence in UV-Vis-IR spectrums for Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (5th Edition of International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering, Issue.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8298582>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bo). *Power Point Presentation on Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds* (School of fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick Campus, Melbourne, Vic-3056, Australia, 2022, Issue.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311145>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bp). *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University;*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bq). *Professional Certificates and Professional achievements of Md. Anowar Hossain.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16572.62089>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286771>

Hossain, M. A. (2023br). *Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Scholarly Community Encyclopedia.*

<https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bs). *Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.*

<https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/49098>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34177.43368>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208384>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal*

Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Optical engineering of fluorescent material and detection; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au

Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bt). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is begging to Mr. António Guterres, the Secretary General of United Nations to stop the conflict between Gaza & Israel.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25967.41129>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10318727>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bu). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bv). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were*

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 BSc in Textile Engg (Wet Processing Tech), City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bx). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>*

Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286941>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15068327>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ca). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978165>

Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023cb). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>

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- Hossain, M. A. (2023cc). *Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics)* (Australia Patent No. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cd). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ce). *Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions; Accepted in Advanced Material Research (2019-2020). School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112357>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cf). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cg). *Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums*. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ch). *UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection*. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

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 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anwar Hossain (Part-02).*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Hossain, M. A. (2024a). Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282484>

Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). *Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888294>

Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>

Hossain, M. A. (2024e). *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds”* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>

Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>

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- Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024l). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024m). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024n). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024o). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'*.

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>

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- Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025a). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government [Grant]*. School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025b). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>
- Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). *Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent*. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>

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- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Abser, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8245079>
- Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. K. (2019). A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(5), 235-240. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-cost-minimization-process-of-heat-and-energy-for-Hossain-Samanta/145246a45b40a7ef33c3e37cc99083f91f6555fa>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>
- Kuniaki Okamoto, T. K., Atsunori Sano *Process for producing 9,10-diphenylanthracene* (United States Patent No. US6566572B2). <https://patents.google.com/patent/US6566572B2/en>
- Mohamed Hamdaoui, A. L., Sabri Halaoua. (2015). Study of Fluorescent Dyeing Process and Influence of Mixture Dyes on High-visibility *Journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics*, 10(1). <http://www.jeffjournal.org>
- Mulliken, R. S. (1971). Role of Kinetic Energy in the Franck–Condon Principle *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 55(1), 309-314. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1675522>

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